

Leptoquark searches at the LHC: Experimental Overview

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Leptoquarks (LQs)

- New scalar (spin 0) or vector (spin 1) particle
 - Carry both lepton and baryon number
 - Carry fractional electric charge $\pm(1/3, 2/3, 4/3, 5/3)e$
- Appear in GUTs, technicolor, composite models, RPV SUSY...
- Current searches assume no intergenerational mixing (FCNC, LFV, proton decay)

- LQs can be singly ($\ell\ell j$) or pair ($\ell\ell jj$) produced

- Free parameters:
 - LQ mass
 - $LQ \rightarrow \ell q$ coupling λ
 - $\beta = \text{BF}(LQ \rightarrow \ell^\pm q) = 1 - \text{BF}(LQ \rightarrow \nu q)$
- Single LQ production cross section depends on λ , pair production does not

Further motivation

- Tension with the SM in decays of B mesons seen at LHCb, BaBar, Belle hint at possible lepton flavor non-universality

R_K	$\frac{BF(B^+ \rightarrow K^+ \mu^+ \mu^-)}{BF(B^+ \rightarrow K^+ e^+ e^-)}$	2.6σ
$R_{K^{*0}}$	$\frac{BF(B^0 \rightarrow K^{*0} \mu^+ \mu^-)}{BF(B^0 \rightarrow K^{*0} e^+ e^-)}$	$2.2-2.5\sigma$
$R_D+R_{D^*}$	$\frac{BF(B \rightarrow D^* \tau \nu)}{BF(B \rightarrow D^* \ell \nu)}$	4σ

Further motivation

- LQs are candidate to explain anomalies at tree level
- Can require mixing of the generations

⇒ Look in particular at
2nd/3rd generations

- Anomalous magnetic moment of the muon a_μ (3.5σ)

[[Phys. Rev. D 73 \(2006\) 072003](#),
[Eur. Phys. J. C 77 \(2017\) 827](#)]

Possible new physics scenarios

$R_D + R_{D^*} \sim 4\sigma$

LQ Searches at the LHC

8 TeV
19.7 fb⁻¹

13 TeV
35.9 fb⁻¹

Single Production

	1st /2nd Generation	3rd Generation
$l\bar{l}q$	$ee j$ $\mu\mu j$	$\tau\tau b$

Pair Production

	1st Generation	2nd Generation	3rd Generation
$l\bar{l}q\bar{q}$	$ee jj$	$\mu\mu jj$	$\tau\tau tt$ $\tau\tau bb$
$l\nu q\bar{q}$	$e\nu jj$	$\mu\nu jj$	$\tau\nu tt$ $\tau\nu bb$
$\nu\nu q\bar{q}$	$\nu\nu jj$		$\nu\nu tt$ $\nu\nu bb$

LQLQ → ee jj, eν jj, μμ jj, μν jj

- 4 channels, similar search strategies
- Select 1 or 2 high momentum e/μ and 2 jets (>50 GeV)
 - No flavor requirement on jets
- Construct LQ candidates which minimize $|M_{LQ1} - M_{LQ2}|$

- Optimize final selection using 3 independent sensitive variables for each LQ mass hypothesis from 200-2000 GeV

- Limit setting via cut-and-count as a function of M_{LQ}

$LQLQ \rightarrow ee jj, e\nu jj, \mu\mu jj, \mu\nu jj$

(CMS-PAS-EXO-17-009)

(arXiv:1808.05082)

[submitted to Phys. Rev. D]

- Limits are expressed as a function of M_{LQ} and extended and combined in $0 < \beta < 1$

- ATLAS search extracts limits through profile-likelihood fit of M_{ej}
- 13TeV (2015) ATLAS results set upper limits of 1100 (1050) GeV for $\beta=1$ in the eejj ($\mu\mu jj$) channel ([arXiv:1605.06035](https://arxiv.org/abs/1605.06035))

LQLQ → ττ bb

(CMS-PAS-EXO-17-016)

- 2τ_{had}+jj

- Require missing p_T and m_{ττ}>100 to suppress QCD and DY backgrounds

- DY, tτ̄ backgrounds taken from MC with data control regions for normalization

- QCD taken from data using ABCD method, shapes validated in control regions

- No flavor tagging on the jets

- already low statistics in the signal region

- Limits extracted using shape of

$$S_T^{MET} = p_T^{\tau_{h,1}} + p_T^{\tau_{h,2}} + p_T^{j_1} + p_T^{j_2} + p_T^{miss}$$

LQLQ \rightarrow $\tau\tau$ bb

- Limits set at 1020 GeV for LQLQ \rightarrow $\tau\tau$ bb ($\beta=1$)

Single LQ $\rightarrow \tau\tau b$

- Single LQ becomes dominant production mode at high M_{LQ} , depending on choice of $LQ \rightarrow \ell q$ coupling λ

JHEP11(2017)044

- Select at least one b-tagged jet, and two τ , separated into $2\tau_{\text{had}}$, $\tau_{\text{had}} + \tau_{\text{lep}(e,\mu)}$ categories
- Limits extracted through simultaneous fit to ST distribution of 3 channels
 - Sensitivity driven by $2\tau_{\text{had}}$ channel

Single LQ $\rightarrow \tau\tau b$

- Exclude $M_{LQ} < 744$ GeV for $\beta=1, \lambda=1$
- Scan $0 < \lambda < 2.5$
 - Upper value of λ bounded by resonance width and LEP constraints

First search for 3rd gen. single LQ production

LQLQ → ττ tt

Build categories from 2τ+2b+2W decay products:

1. **Opposite-sign (e/μ + τ_{had}) + b jet**

2. **Same-sign (e/μ + τ_{had}) + b jet**

- Further split into low and high $S_T = \sum p_T(\text{jets, leptons, MET})$ regions

- Reconstruct top candidate by choosing 3jet combination closest to top mass

- Use data control region with inverted τ_{had} isolation, corrected for kinematical differences, to estimate tτ̄, W+jets backgrounds

- **Fit top p_T to extract limits**

3. **e/μ + 2τ_{had}**

- Main backgrounds from jets faking hadronic taus
- Multiple data control regions used to estimate backgrounds
- **Limits set via counting experiment**

LQLQ \rightarrow $\tau\tau$ tt

- All categories recombined
- Limits set as a function of M_{LQ} for $\beta=1$ and in 2D β vs M_{LQ} plane

LQLQ \rightarrow 2v qq/bb/tt

(arXiv:1805.10228)
Accepted by Phys. Rev. D

- Reinterpretation of SUSY searches for squark pair production
 - $\tilde{q} \rightarrow q + \tilde{\chi}$ equivalent to $LQ \rightarrow q + \nu$ in the $\tilde{\chi} \rightarrow 0$ limit
- Perform search for light jets, b jets, t jets
- Many categories, different sensitivities in different channels
 - Most sensitive categories for $\nu\nu$ tt channel require large $M_{T2} > 1500$ GeV, 4-6 jets, and 1 or 2 b-tagged jets

LQLQ \rightarrow 2v qq/bb/tt

(arXiv:1805.10228)
Accepted by Phys. Rev. D

- Squark signal sample acceptance and kinematics seen to be consistent with LQ signal for both scalar and vector LQ
- Assume $\beta=0$, also add $\beta=1/2$ for ttvv, motivated by model in [JHEP11\(2017\)044](#)

Observed Limits (GeV)	Scalar $\beta=0$	Vector $\beta=0$	Vector $\beta=1/2$
vv qq	980	1790	
vv bb	1100	1810	
vv tt	1020	1780	1530

LQ cross sections from [arXiv:1801.07641](#)

LQLQ → μμ tt

(arXiv:1809.05558)
Submitted to Phys. Rev. Lett.

First search to mix generations!

- Require 2 oppositely charged muons ($m_{\mu\mu} > 110$) and 2 top quarks. Requirements on $S_T^{\text{lep}} = \sum p_T(\text{leptons})$ and $S_T = \sum p_T(\text{jets, leptons, MET})$

- Split signal region into distinct categories:

1. At least one additional muon or electron

- Backgrounds taken from MC, e/μ misidentification rate measured in data
- Reconstruct M_{LQ} from $LQ \rightarrow \mu t (\rightarrow bW (\rightarrow \ell\nu))$
- Fit M_{LQ} to extract limits

2. All other events

- Estimate DY and $t\bar{t}$ backgrounds simultaneously with $(\geq 2e, 0\mu)$ data sample
- Fit S_T to extract limits

	1 st	2 nd	3 rd
Quarks	u up	c charm	t top
	d down	s strange	b beauty
Leptons	e electron	μ muon	τ tau
	ν_e neutrino electron	ν_μ neutrino muon	ν_τ neutrino tau

LQLQ \rightarrow $\mu\mu$ $t\bar{t}$

(arXiv:1809.05558)
Submitted to Phys. Rev. Lett.

- Results combined with previous LQ \rightarrow $t\bar{t}$ and LQ \rightarrow bv searches to produce limits expressed as a function of

$$\text{BF}(\text{LQ} \rightarrow \mu t) = 1 - \text{BF}(\text{LQ} \rightarrow t\bar{t}) \text{ or } \text{BF}(\text{LQ} \rightarrow \mu t) = 1 - \text{BF}(\text{LQ} \rightarrow bv)$$

- $M_{\text{LQ}} < 1420 \text{ GeV}$ excluded for LQLQ \rightarrow $\mu\mu$ $t\bar{t}$ ($\beta=1$)
- $M_{\text{LQ}} < 900 \text{ GeV}$ excluded for μt , $t\bar{t}$
- $M_{\text{LQ}} < 980 \text{ GeV}$ excluded for μt , bv

LQ Limit Overview

8 TeV
19.7 fb⁻¹

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Summary

- Intriguing hints of new physics in B meson decays from LHCb have renewed interest in LQs, particularly with 3rd generation quarks
- The LHC has a large and expanding program of leptoquark searches, up to now led by CMS
 - Most channels push sensitivity above the TeV scale, favored by B flavor anomalies
 - Most searches still assume no mixing of the generations, but we are starting to investigate final states or model phase space not previously considered
- Eagerly await updates from our LHCb colleagues
- Searches adding or using 2017/2018 data in progress, stay tuned!

